

FOODPathS communication, dissemination, exploitation Plan

DELIVERABLE 8.1 – PLAN FOR C&D&E ACTIVITIES

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Plan for C&D&E activities

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1. Executive summary

This deliverable presents a comprehensive plan of the communication, dissemination and exploitation (CDE) activities planned for the FOODPathS project, as well as the associated actions to be carried out during the project. This plan falls under the first task of Work Package 8: “Co-creating the pathway to impact: a multi-level communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy”.

EUFIC as WP8 leader, in close collaboration with the project coordination team, task leaders and the entire consortium, is responsible for carefully designing, preparing, and implementing the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities during the FOODPathS project lifespan.

Starting from the actors with whom the project will interact now and in the future – with various levels of engagement – **the plan identifies 13 target audiences**. They are all addressed by specific communication and dissemination activities developed according to their needs and the level of relevance for the FOODPathS’s scopes and expected impacts. The **14 tools and activities** that will be developed by November 2024 (before the launch and piloting of the Prototype, as shown by the timeline in §7), **are the following**:

- Brand Identity
- Website
- Database
- Press releases
- Social Networks
- Other (traditional) media outlets
- SFSN – Sustainable Food Systems Network
- Podcasts
- Webinars
- Leaflets, brochures and factsheets
- Project presentations and articles
- Conferences and events
- Networking activities
- Other C&D activities

For each of them, **specific Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) were fixed** (§6), to monitor and assess the activities and the overall strategy, thus enabling the consortium to fine-tune the provisions contained in this document and plan in more detail the actions to be implemented during the next years and until the end of the project. Indeed, **this deliverable has the characteristic of being a living document that will be updated throughout the project**. This allows the improvements of activities based on results achieved, lessons learned, feedback collected from target audiences and actors interacting with FOODPathS (i.e., thanks to periodical meetings with the Advisory Board Members and the SCAR Food Systems Working Group members); it also considers possible changes in the scenarios in which the project operates. Given this, the procedures and timeline to revise the plan were identified and agreed upon with the core partners involved (ZonMw, INRAE, IT and other WP Leaders and WP Deputy Leaders).

Moreover, **this plan identifies a first version of the exploitation strategy**, to be detailed and consolidated in a later stage of the project. So far, and thanks to the contribution of WP leaders and WP Deputy Leaders, **12 Key Exploitable Results (KERs)** were defined. This will be done together with the target audiences potentially interested in using them and taking into account the actions to be implemented to fully exploit them.

The document contains also a detailed process explaining how the project partners’ contributions will be coordinated, ensuring that FOODPathS will communicate, disseminate and exploit results using one voice.

After the first three months of the FOODPathS project – dedicated mainly to the co-creation of this plan and to the operational elements of it (brand identity, website, etc.) – the next steps concern relevant tests of the strategy presented in this plan. Given this, in May 2023 the activities will be assessed through the fixed KPI. A discussion with partners will be conducted during the annual meeting, to fine-tune the strategy and agree on a more detailed plan for the second year of FOODPathS.

2. Introduction

FOODPathS aims to design a prototype for the future Sustainable Food Systems (SFS) Partnership in Europe. This prototype will offer a concrete pathway on how the future Partnership should function from 2024 onwards, covering all its components with recommendations based on the experience gained during the FOODPathS project. The Prototype will include co-funding strategies, a governance model, *Modus Operandi*, a sustainability charter, a strategic research and innovation agenda (SRIA), and a series of co-creation cases, among others. Potential trade-offs of proposed activities, including effective communication, dissemination and exploitation (C&D&E) strategies – resulting from the efforts of involving local and global stakeholders in shaping the future Partnership – will be proposed as examples to be pursued.

The **Plan for C&D&E** (D8.1) is part of the Work Package (WP) 8 and **aims to communicate, disseminate and exploit the project's activities and results widely and beyond the project consortium, by involving all the partner networks.**

In this framework, the C&D&E strategies described in this plan seek to engage all relevant stakeholders in the co-creation and launch of the SFS Partnership Prototype. The proposed collaborations will help to achieve the expected outcomes with the greatest possible impact by providing stakeholders at the European, national and regional levels, with relevant information on the FOODPathS project's activities and achievements, as well as by defining the strategy for the exploitation of the project's results and their sustainability after the end of the grant period.

This plan contains detailed information on the C&D&E actions, timing, and target groups, which are based on the discussions that took place during the Kick-off Meeting (KoM). Here, all partners had the opportunity to provide feedback on the strategies that would work best for each target group based on their expertise. The co-creation of this plan continued with 2 rounds of feedback on the plan and an internal online workshop held on the 24th of August 2022 with at least 1 representative of each partner organization, to address pending comments and decisions and to finalize the plan.

This plan is meant to be a living document that will be monitored and assessed – also thanks to the provision of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) – every 12 months, starting from May 2023, to fine-tune the entire strategy. Moreover, insights and suggestions on how to improve the communication and dissemination activities will be gathered thanks to periodical meetings with the Advisory Board Members and the SCAR SWG FS members.

The plan is composed of 10 chapters. After the Executive Summary (§1) and the Introduction (§2), the objectives of the plan are presented (§3), followed by an analysis of the target audiences addressed and their needs and expectations (§4). Based on these, the implementation of activities and tools is described in detail (§5): the description is completed by the analysis of their interactions with the various target groups. Chapter 6 shows the timeline in which the actions are expected to be implemented, followed by the KPIs for assessing and fine-tuning the plan in the future (§7). In Chapter 8, the plan describes the first version of the exploitation strategy, presenting the Key Exploitation Results (KERs) and the guidelines on how they will be exploited by the end of the project. The plan ends by describing the operational process to guarantee the effective implementation of the provisions of this document (§9) and the next steps (§10). Complementary documents mentioned throughout this plan can be found in the Annex section, at the end of this document.

This plan has been conceived according to the Technical Annex of the FOODPathS project in compliance with the Ethics requirements and guidelines. It also incorporates the recommendations set in the Horizon Europe documents and guidelines:

- [Horizon Europe - Dissemination & Exploitation](#)
- [Communicating about your EU-funded project](#)

3. Objectives of the Plan

The main objective of this plan is to offer partners a set of guidelines, responsibilities, and timelines on how/when/where to communicate, disseminate and exploit the results of the project, as well as to encourage them to use their channels (organisations websites, social networks, etc.) to support the communication and dissemination activities.

The plan will ensure a set of actions coherent with the communication strategy, by gathering the ideal conditions to:

- create the project's identity;
- position the project and main outcomes at the macro level of the European SFS Partnership;
- engage actors from the entire Food System to contribute and co-create the SFS Partnership Prototype, and build impactful relationships;
- communicate, disseminate and exploit the project's outcomes successfully.

Objectives of the plan		Main actions
1.	Coordinate, streamline and support all C&D&E activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providing clear guidelines on how to communicate, disseminate and exploit results
2.	Help forging and sustaining relationships between organisations, networks and people from the consortium and future Partnership, actively involving various audiences in the project's exploitation and sustainability measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Defining target groups and their needs • Defining specific C&D&E strategies for each target group • Provide relevant content (e.g., best practices, reports for policies and strategies) based on the need of each target group. • Networking activities and linking with institutions
3.	Support reaching expected outcomes and impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Revising the strategies every year • By setting KPIs
4.	Raise awareness of the project activities and results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sharing experiences, driving progress
5.	Communicate and disseminate the findings and results among target audiences;	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing relevant content based on specific C&D&E strategies for each target group
6.	Engage target audiences that will benefit from the project's results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Networking activities and linking with identified actors • Sharing of experiences, driving progress • Defining specific C&D&E strategies for each target group

Table 1 - Objectives of the plan and main actions implemented

4. Target audiences

The definition of FOODPathS target audiences is far from simple. It requires insights in the complexity of FS, and the comprehension of who are the actors interacting within and beyond the project; the latter concern all involved in the development and implementation of the future partnership, however, also all others that are interested in its future actions. Moreover, it is important to define what are their respective needs. Thus, chapter 4 presents the actors that will interact with FOODPathS and how they are translated into “target audiences” for the present plan. Before presenting them and the messages delivered to them in detail, the targets’ needs are first outlined. A table resuming the target audiences, their needs and the (to be) delivered messages is available in ANNEX I.

4.1. Current and future actors interacting with FOODPathS

The Development and Execution of the future SFS Partnership request the involvement of a wide variety of actors at different levels of engagement in time. In the full trajectory, DG-RTD EC and the SCAR WG FS are guiding the process, hence have the highest engagement level. They take care of the narrative, template, SRIA, launching of the call for the future Partnership SFS and even support the development of the Legal Framework for SFS. They are a continuously relevant actor for FOODPathS. Other actors will become involved along the way, as presented below.

June 2022 – December 2025

During the preparatory trajectory to build the Prototype Partnership SFS and also during the guidance phase of the future Partnership consortium, the strategy of the FOODPathS project consortium is to target as many different actors as possible. This is asked by the EC using the expression ‘*being as inclusive as possible*’ and stated in the call text that funded this project. The objective is twofold: to inform the wide audience of different actors and get their feedback on all building blocks of the Partnership (SRIA, Governance Model, *Modus Operandi*, Communication Strategy, etc.). In paving the way for the future partnership, the various actors will engage differently, starting with the highest and ending with the lowest level:

- I. **direct partners in FOODPaths**, who are the beneficiaries of the granted FOODPathS project and are asked to implement a series of activities in close collaboration with other actors to pave the way to the future partnership;
- II. **Network organisations represented by the Partners**, who are wide and trans-national organisations able to represent the interests of a plurality of actors, that will be involved in the partnership prototype development through (I);
- III. **Advisory Board members and their institutions**, that will support the efficient design of the prototype with their knowledge and expertise;
- IV. **the widest public**, the main beneficiaries of the social, environmental and economic impacts that the project seeks to generate in the long-term.

The listed ones are the currently existing actors that must be considered in the FOODPathS implementation actions by all WPs, not only for communication, dissemination and exploitation activities. However, other actors will affect FOODPathS in the coming years and, thus, should be considered as well.

2024 – 2031 (7 years), hence future actors to be already now considered!

As a response to the future HorizonEurope call for funding Work Programme, a Consortium will be formed, essentially with partners from ministries and funding agencies. If granted, in 2024 they will form the **Consortium of the future Partnership SFS**. In the eyes of the European Commission, they are called *beneficiaries*, because they will benefit from the EC grant of about 170 M€; this represents 30% of the budget. The beneficiaries are at the same time co-funders, guaranteeing to provide the remaining 70% of the total budget (approx 600 M€). **For simplicity, we call this target group: “Partners of the future Partnership SFS Consortium”.**

This future Partnership will most likely launch calls to which new consortia of applicants – in this case thanks to the funding provided by the future Partnership SFS – will respond. These applicants may be public or private parties (e.g. universities or companies), NGOs, foundations, etc. **For simplicity, we may call this group of actors: “Applicants of future Partnership SFS Funding”.**

It should be noted that **there can be additional Partners of the future Partnership SFS Consortium**, who are willing to co-fund (in cash and/or in-kind) the Partnership SFS, like regions (e.g., via European Structural Funds), private

partners, foundations, research organisations, etc. If there is an internal executive program proposed and agreed upon by the EC, all these partners have the right to perform activities (like research or innovation actions). However, in all cases, *conflicts of interest* are to be avoided, meaning that these partners thus cannot be ‘Applicants of future Partnership SFS Grants’ at the same time.

From 2031

The idea of the financial support for the future Partnership is that there will be “a lasting Consortium/Cluster/Network/Partnership/...” active after 2031, i.e., the end of the EC-Granted Future Partnership SFS. For simplicity, we may call this target group “*Potential future Partnership SFS Consortium*”. This future target group is also already now considered, because it will play a key role in realizing the already stated sustainability targets. Its organisational structure needs to be established in the 2024 – 2031 period to guarantee success. The nature of Partners will be highly diverse to mobilize all actors to realise the transition towards SFS.

4.2. From “actors” to “target audiences”

How does the (“expanding”) universe of actors interacting with FOODPathS affect the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities? How could the FOODPathS WP8 support the other WPs ensuring that the relevant actors are involved with the appropriate level of engagement? How could a plan be designed including the most suitable measures to realise the objectives of the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities?

The posed questions could be only addressed by the identification of target audiences of the FOODPathS CDE Plan (which defines the strategy and design of the future communication, dissemination and exploitation activities, as well as support the other WPs in the engagement of stakeholders for their activities). Here, we have in mind the current and future actors collaborating with the project partners and their different levels of engagement.

Considering this, **we refer to the “target audience” as a group of people/entities/stakeholders with common needs**. They will timely receive specific messages (defined and tailored to such needs) through different channels and tools depending on project activities. Our purpose is to actively involve/engage them in one or more of the WP activities. We also communicate what FOODPathS is realising thanks to the public-funded contribution of the EC, disseminate the results and ease their exploitation and/or adoption by actors external to the FOODPathS consortium. **Target audiences are defined with the scope to make them recognisable as a group and/or to have common key elements distinguishing them from other ones.**

So far, the FOODPathS CDE Plan target audiences are:

- Partners of the future Partnership SFS Consortium (from 2024)
- Networks of FOODPathS Partners
- Policymakers
- Policymakers supporting organisations
- Actors of the FS
- Educators
- Research performers
- Civil society organisations and consumer organisations
- Citizens and consumers
- Philanthropic organisations
- Financers
- Other related partnerships
- Coordinators of other funded projects

To support the creation of an ecosystem that will allow the long-term prosperity of the partnership – thus facilitating the work of the partners of the future Partnership SFS Consortium – it is important to consider the role and involvement that these target audiences could have both as Applicants of future Partnership SFS Funding and as Actors in the Long-Lasting SFS Cluster. Indeed, the CDE activities will be designed to trigger and motivate them to take an active role in joining one of the two categories of actors.

In particular, the table below shows in which of the two categories the target audiences could fall in the future:

FOODPathS target audiences	Potential partner in the future Partnership SFS Consortium	Potential Applicants of future Partnership Funding
Partners of the future Partnership SFS Consortium	YES	NO
Networks of FOODPathS Partners	Partially YES	Partially YES
Policymakers	Partially YES	NO
Policymakers supporting organisations	Partially YES	NO
Actors of the FS	Partially YES	YES
Educators	NO	YES
Research performers	NO	YES
Civil society organisations and consumers organisations	Partially YES	YES
Citizens and consumers	NO	NO
Philanthropic organisations	YES	YES
Financers	YES	NO
Other related partnerships	NO	NO
Coordinators of other funded projects	NO	NO

Table 2 - Potential future role of the target audiences

4.3. Target audiences' needs

FOODPathS and its activities are designed based on the target audiences' needs (defined already during the proposal preparation), which are the following:

- Facilitate synergies in the European Research Area (ERA) for Sustainable Food Systems (SFS) by better coordination, more ambitious, 'visible' and impactful research funding across the Member States (MS), convening Research and Innovation (R&I) public and private funders to shape the Food Systems (FS);
- Alignment of co-funded calls by MS based on joint research strategies to leverage national funding;
- A Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA), integrating urban and regional FS strategies;
- Need to support and liaise with ongoing initiatives, such as the SCAR Strategic Working Group FS (SCAR SWG FS), other Partnerships, and international organisations to ensure holistic and inclusive approaches, avoiding ERA fragmentation and funding overlap;
- Engagement of all FS actors including at large to reach sustainable FS;
- Education and training programs for the leaders of tomorrow's FS transition.

4.4. Target audiences analysis

In this paragraph, all the target audiences listed in §4.2 are analysed in detail, describing who they are and how they will be addressed by FOODPathS activities, presenting also the messages to be delivered to them.

4.4.1. Partners of the future Partnership SFS Consortium

Who are they? | As explained in §4.1, they are the entities identified by the EC through a call to establish the partnership and co-fund the SRIA implementation activities. They represent a crucial target audience for FOODPathS since the large majority of the activities are designed to ease their future work and they will be engaged closely during the project lifetime. Considering this, they will represent the most important target in terms of exploitation activities.

Messages | The following messages should be transferred to them thanks to the activities of the CDE Plan:

- The FOODPathS project is paving the way for your future activities: the effective and successful launch of the partnership depends on our mutual collaboration;
- FOODPathS will work to facilitate the dialogue between the partners of the future Partnership SFS Consortium and all the other actors, to ensure that everybody will be involved and contribute to the transformation of the FS;
- FOODPathS results will represent a source for developing and improving the future partnership.

4.4.2. Network of FOODPathS partners

Who are they? | All the networks, in which FOODPathS partners are members of (i.e. COPA-COGECA, Milan Urban Food Policy Pact – MUFPP, etc.) or coordinators (i.e. SUSFOOD, the European Technology Platform Food for Life, BIOEAST WG FS, ERIAFF Network, etc.), fall in this target audience. This represents a key group to ensure the achievement of wider impacts. One of the FOODPathS strengths is that each partner represents one or more networks in the FS; they serve as potential multipliers, they can convey communication and dissemination messages to a larger group of people and stakeholders, also increasing the FOODPathS exploitation opportunities. Consequently, such networks will be engaged directly in the project activities, or they can help in the stakeholders' engagement, supporting the identification and involvement of the right and most influential actors (in particular the ones that could become partners of the future Partnership SFS Consortium). Finally, several results of FOODPathS can feed the partners' network activities.

The following figure provides an overview of the networks in which the FOODPathS partners are currently involved.

Figure 1 – Networks managed or to whom the FOODPathS partners belong to

Messages | The following messages should be transferred to them according to the CDE Plan:

- FOODPathS is producing results that can feed and improve your activities;
- It is worthwhile to convey the FOODPathS findings and activities within your network;
- The FOODPathS network will include your contributions in the SRIA development and other project's activities, especially also in the vitrine of case studies;
- You are asked to support FOODPathS to engage stakeholders and motivate key actors in becoming co-funders of the future partnership;
- You will receive information and get involved in the co-creation of the future SFS partnership.

4.4.3. Policymakers

Who are they? | Actors under this subgroup are still heterogeneous (for example, differing at the governance level), however, they are associated by a common feature: the power to influence and/or change policies related to FS. According to project purposes, FOODPathS will address the policymakers of all levels: local (cities and Regions), national (MS, mainly represented by their Ministries and/or owned funding agencies), European (the European Commission) and international (FAO, UN, etc.). Moreover, several of them have the political mandate, the interest, and the resources to co-fund the R&I activities defined through the partnership. Considering the importance they have for the effective establishment of the future SFS Partnership, including the creation of an adequate budget to fund and implement the actions contained in the SRIA, FOODPathS will put a lot of effort in interactively engaging them, integrating the information that the project can provide within exchange and co-creative meetings.

Finally, during the SRIA preparation, FOODPathS will deliver guidelines and insights on how to engage policymakers in defining their knowledge needs.

Messages | The following messages should be transferred thanks to the activities of the CDE Plan:

- Climate change already impacts agriculture and food systems, challenging their resilience: thus, there is an urgency to act in implementing policies and strategies on FS and to critically review existing policies to stay within planetary boundaries;
- FS have become a particularly hot topic in recent years, with far-reaching impacts across many dimensions (e.g., geopolitical, economic, environmental, and health). We urgently need to build the governance foundations for an effective FS management at the European level – ultimately leading to improved food security, sustainability, and resilience across all levels;
- FOODPathS activities and the SFS partnership prototype will help policy makers to realize the sustainability targets and policies set at the National, European (e.g. Farm to Fork strategy) and International levels;
- FOODPathS partners can provide actionable knowledge to improve policies at all levels; moreover, the case studies can support you in evaluating policies implemented;
- A real commitment – in terms of policy development and resources – is needed to make the partnership work and implement the SRIA;
- FOODPathS can contribute to guaranteeing the coherence of the ERA on FS and align the R&I actions and funds among different MS and governance levels while respecting different priorities;
- Cities and regions can influence the FOODPathS SRIA;
- FOODPathS will support more effective multi-level governance for food systems, including better coordination between European, national and sub-national actors (e.g. regions, cities);
- FOODPathS offers information on the future Partnership development and co-creation of important features, e.g. R&I procedures following a systems approach;
- The development of Food Systems Living Labs will allow for the engagement of a wide range of stakeholders at the country-regional-local level to jointly tackle concrete, real-life (R&I) food system challenges, including unusual suspects and those who do not usually work together.

4.4.4. Policymakers supporting organisations

Who are they? | This category groups the European and national agencies that support the work of policymakers with studies, working documents, suggestions for improving policies, etc., such as JRC, EFSA, SCAR FS SWG, and EIP-AGRI. They have a political mandate and interest to inform policymakers' choices, proposing changes and possible R&I actions to be funded in the future. Considering this, a constant dialogue with them is needed to make sure that FOODPathS and the Prototype contribute to informing their work, are in line with their strategies, as well as to increase the opportunity to fully engage the policymakers.

Messages | The following messages should be transferred thanks to the activities of the CDE Plan:

- Building a collaborative and structured dialogue is essential to join forces toward sustainable FS;
- R&I activities contained in the SRIA could address agencies' long-term objectives;
- Working together leads to a stronger commitment from policymakers in taking actions in the future SFS Partnership;
- The development of Food Systems Living Labs will allow for the engagement of a wide range of stakeholders at a country-regional-local level to jointly tackle concrete, real-life (R&I) food system challenges, including unusual suspects and those who don't usually work together;
- Effective FS governance is key to building a more resilient European FS.

4.4.5. Actors of the FS

Who are they? | This group covers all the actors working along the value chain, from farm to fork, such as farmers and their cooperatives, food processors, retailers, HoReCa, input suppliers, packaging companies, etc. Actors in this target audience are mainly private for-profit entities; but, also the non-profit cooperatives and social enterprises are included. Moreover, in addition to the sector in which they work, they differentiate in size (micro, small, medium, large) and geographical presence (local, regional, national, and international). These existing differences among the actors of the group influence also their possibility to access and adopt innovations due to the existence of

barriers (i.e. smaller players have fewer resources to invest, language could represent a barrier for some of them, etc.). Finally, they represent a relevant target for future calls to be launched by the SFS Partnership. To reach a greater impact, these actors will be engaged mainly through their representing organisations, which will be used as “multipliers”. Many of these representing organisations (i.e., FoodDrinkEurope, CopaCogeca, National Food Technology Platforms, etc.) are already in the FOODPathS Consortium as a partner or related to other project partners.

Messages | The following messages should be transferred thanks to the activities of the CDE Plan:

- The point of view of the different actors in food systems will be considered in the SRIA preparation and their needs will be taken into account;
- The SRIA will enable the development and uptake of innovations that will transform the way we produce food, ensuring the transition towards sustainable FS;
- Insight into existing barriers and trade-offs will be communicated to reduce the obstacles to the wide R&I results uptake;
- The SFS partnership prototype shall set the grounds for a platform where precompetitive R&I actions are conducted, aiming for sustainable solutions for some of the current challenges;
- The development of Food Systems Living Labs will allow structures at a country-regional level where thematic challenges could be tackled allowing the involvement of the private sector (including businesses that are not usually tackled by R&I EU funding);
- Staying informed of FOODPathS initiatives (SRIA, universities network, living labs, etc.) has clear added value as you will be in the loop of upcoming policies and assorted incentives addressing food systems and their R&I aspects;
- The partnership will foster the collaboration of the actors of the FS with the public sector, as well as with other operators in the food value chain, creating an environment suitable for open innovation and collaborative R&I processes among all actors.

4.4.6. Educators

Who are they? | This group contains all the Higher Education Institutes (universities, universities of applied sciences or polytechnics), in particular the ones offering courses in the FS domain to students, but also professional training centers (WP5). This target audience has a twofold “soul”: on one hand, it has the decision makers of such entities (i.e. the rectors and their association, pro-rectors on research and innovation, etc.), since they are responsible for the strategic choices on the courses offered; on the other hand, the group contains also the educators actively involved in the delivery of the courses.

Moreover, considering the activities implemented by FOODPathS (mainly in WP5), the **target group could include actors delivering non-formal education activities and working in the applied (vocational) levels of education to cover life-long learning (from childhood to experience employees)**: however, they will mainly be covered via collaboration activities developed by other projects that have them as a specific focus (please, see §4.1.3).

The engagement of this target group will impact the students at the higher education institutes participating in FOODPathS activities since they will benefit from an improved training system and be able to transfer the knowledge acquired to other target audiences (i.e. the food chain actors). Thanks to this, FOODPathS will train the leaders of tomorrow’s FS transition.

Additionally, the universities and their local ecosystems may play a pivotal role in demonstrating SFS cases, hence being exemplary for other FS actors and the wider civil society.

Finally, the higher education institutes and their staff will be interested in the SRIA developed by FOODPathS, since it will define the future priorities in the sector and, after the co-funders engagement, the calls for funding their research projects.

Messages | The following messages should be transferred thanks to the activities of the CDE Plan:

- FOODPathS aims to improve the FS education and training programs by helping to fill existing knowledge gaps and upskilling students;
- The adhesion to the FOODPathS European branded network of universities working on FS will increase the visibility of institutions as exemplary organisations in the transition towards SFS, and help them to attract more students;
- By connecting with other actors of the FS, FOODPathS will improve the quality and the content of academic courses on FS, aligning them to their needs and introducing practical knowledge;

- Integrating FOODPathS knowledge, academic curricula will be aligned with strategic R&I priorities in the FS, thus preparing students and researchers to catch all the future occasions coming from the partnership's funding program;
- Rectors and educators can be part of the participatory process to exchange experiences in designing and implementing training courses for sustainable FS;
- Educators and academic voices will be heard in the preparation of the SRIA and their needs will be shared with policymakers thanks to FOODPathS;
- The development of Food Systems Living Labs will allow for the engagement of a wide range of stakeholders at a country-regional-local level to jointly tackle concrete, real-life (R&I) food system challenges, including unusual suspects and those who do not usually work together;
- Educators joining the FOODPathS network will have an opportunity to connect and exchange with pioneering universities across Europe, educators and universities' networks (i.e. EURAGRI, FOODforce, etc.) and to develop new collaborations.

4.4.7. Research performers

Who are they? | This group includes all the organisations performing research activities at the national and European levels, covering all the different components of the FS (policy and regulatory effectiveness, farming, processing, logistic, etc.) and expertise (soil, bioeconomy, mobility, etc.), since adopting multi-, inter- and trans-disciplinary approaches among all the disciplines, integrating knowledge and expertise, is essential to support the transition toward sustainable FS. Their activities are also to inform the policymakers with data and science-based information to improve the quality of the current legislation since the transformation we aim to achieve can only happen when a functioning regulatory framework (including effective policies and enforcement) exists. Considering this, research organisations have an interest in the SRIA, which will identify the R&I priorities for the future, reinforcing their relations with policymakers and reaching market innovations thanks to the collaboration with (public or private) funders and food chain actors.

Messages | The following messages should be transferred thanks to the activities of the CDE Plan:

- Research centres' voices and points of view will be heard to develop the SRIA;
- FOODPathS can support research organisations in improving their collaboration with policymakers, empowering them with science-based information;
- The prototype and the future partnership are a great opportunity to get support for research centres activities in the FS;
- FOODPathS can support the networking with other target audiences to increase the rate of uptake of research outputs;
- FOODPathS will work on supportive measures for future project partners funded under the SFS Partnership to enable additional added values through transnational cooperation (e.g. networking, training, capacity building);
- The development of Food Systems Living Labs will allow for the engagement of a wide range of stakeholders at a country-regional-local level to jointly tackle concrete, real-life (R&I) food system challenges, including unusual suspects and those who do not usually work together.

4.4.8. Civil society organisations and consumers organisations

Who are they? | This target is constituted by all the organisations representing citizens' and consumers' needs and interests, as well as focusing on social and environmental challenges. Such a target has a crucial role in connecting FOODPathS with the large public. Indeed, considering the scope and the activities of the project, the requests coming from the society should be taken into account in the SRIA and in the prototype definition, to realise a large impact and benefits for all, leaving nobody behind. Considering how FOODPathS is designed, the scopes and the budget, the project will mainly listen to citizens' and consumers' voices through their representatives and the involvement of representatives in the project Advisory Board. In addition, the organisations considered in this target group are also reinforcing their visions and positions with studies and research activities, that can add value to the FOODPathS SRIA and the debates to be held in the Mirror Groups (WP7).

The project will address the civil society and consumer organisations operating at local, national, European and International levels. In addition, considering that FOODPathS activities are inspired by the will to provide a better world to future generations and the attention that the youngest are affected by climate change and the environment, the project will consider the engagement of organisations representing young people (i.e., Fridays For Future/Youth for Climate, Slow Food Youth Network, European Youth Forum, Bioeconomy Youth Ambassadors, etc.) for example with their involvement in Mirror Groups.

Finally, their involvement and active participation are crucial to guarantee that the FOODPathS main results and legacy are not misinterpreted by society, causing a repulsion and not acceptance of them.

Messages | The following messages should be transferred thanks to the activities of the CDE Plan:

- FOODPathS want to listen to the citizens' and consumers' perspectives and needs, including them in the SRIA and the prototype for the partnership;
- Thanks to the FOODPaths activities, organisations representing citizens and consumers will have their voice in the future partnership;
- The development of Food Systems Living Labs will allow for the engagement of a wide range of stakeholders at a country-regional-local level to jointly tackle concrete, real-life (R&I) food system challenges, including unusual suspects and those who do not usually work together;
- FOODPathS will give tangible examples of how such organisations can participate and contribute;
- They support FOODPathS to correctly communicate their activities and results, to avoid their rejection from society; on the contrary, they will support the snowball effect of positive trajectories;
- Consumers are the 'final users' of food system products, so a better understanding of their needs is crucial.

4.4.9. Citizens and consumers

Who are they? | The large public – in their role as citizens, players in professional FS activities, as well as more specifically in their role as consumers making consumption choices – is the group on which FOODPathS aims to create wider long-term impacts, thanks to the achievement of all its objectives. However, considering the limitations in time and budget of project activities and the enormous diversity of citizens, they are considered an “indirect” target group; their interests and needs will be represented and integrated through their representatives (§4.1.5), engaged in different projects' activities (and with a specific focus in WP7). Considering this, they will be in any case reached by the FOODPathS communication activities, which can be realised also together with other targets (i.e. partners' networks and/or other EU-funded projects) or public ambassadors (i.e. influencers, multipliers, etc.) to have a higher outreach and relevance. In doing this, it is extremely relevant that citizens and consumers have a correct perception of the FOODPathS objectives and activities, to avoid possible rejection from their side. Finally, for the same reasons explained in the previous paragraph, the project will implement specific communication activities, by itself or in collaboration with other actors, addressed to the young generations.

Messages | The following messages should be transferred thanks to the activities of the CDE Plan:

- Today FS are not sustainable; therefore, the EC wants to support a joint action of different actors to make them sustainable: FOODPathS is the project that is preparing this joint action;
- The benefits will be highlighted of having safe and sustainable consumption choices that are affordable to all;
- The potential trade-offs and perceived negative consequences of difficult choices to be made are underlined: we will be transparent and honest about difficult choices to be made;
- The future Partnership will create new opportunities for sustainable and healthy diets;
- The development of Food Systems Living Labs will allow for the engagement of citizens at a country-regional-local level to jointly tackle concrete, real-life (R&I) food system challenges, including unusual suspects and those who do not usually work together.

4.4.10. Philanthropic organisations

Who are they? | This group consists of all the foundations and philanthropic organisations (considered individually or in their associative networks) committed to be involved in actions that are making FS sustainable. Actors in the group differ from each other in their scope and mission, the typology, the field of their expertise and funding programs, and the level of their actions (national, European, international): such existing differences must be considered when delivering dissemination and communication activities aiming to fully engage them in the prototype development and commit them in becoming full partners or beneficiaries in the future partnership to co-coordinate the transition to SFS.

In addition to the ones already working directly in the field of the FS, FOODPathS will target philanthropic organisations in related sectors, such as environmental topics, just and fair transitions, integration of vulnerable people, etc. The scope is twofold: on one hand, the project would like to raise awareness for FS transitions, easing the integration in their scopes and activities; on the other hand, they provide best practices from which FOODPathS can learn.

Messages | The following messages should be transferred thanks to the activities of the CDE Plan:

- FOODPathS wants to learn from the philanthropic organisations and their best (and worst) practices, thanks to their engagement and involvement in various activities (i.e. WP2, WP7, etc.);
- Philanthropic organisations are welcomed in the future partnership, both in the governance model, as co-funders and as beneficiaries;
- FOODPathS aims to increase awareness of the value of working on food systems with philanthropic organisations own target groups;
- It will explain how actions to enable the transition toward a sustainable FS could be integrated into philanthropic organisations scopes;
- The development of Food Systems Living Labs will allow for the engagement of a wide range of stakeholders at a country-regional-local level to jointly tackle concrete, real-life (R&I) food system challenges, including unusual suspects and those who do not usually work together.

4.4.11. Financers

Who are they? | Actors under this category are represented by a wide spectrum of investors, that could be institutional banks controlled by the public sector (i.e. the European Investment Bank – EIB), private banks, equity funds, business angels, venture capitals, pension funds and insurance banks interested in investing in food and environmental sectors, etc. They can operate at national, European or international levels and they represent potential funders of the future partnership.

To have their commitment, it is relevant to use leverage on financial elements that could attract their interest, for instance, the aspects related to sustainable investments, the impact that finance can have on the climate transition, etc. At the same time, FOODPathS should explain how investing in making the FS sustainable could represent an added value for some of their client. Finally, the project, thanks to the SRIA and its implementation, could help the actors in this target to find innovators with promising results and products with relevant added value for FS, climate, environment, and society to support.

Messages | The following messages should be transferred thanks to the activities of the CDE Plan:

- FOODPathS can add value to financers' investments (and to their clients) thanks to R&I solutions easing the transition to SFS;
- Becoming a funder of the future partnership means playing an active role to make the FS sustainable and creating an impact on society;
- Investing in partnership solutions can reduce the price of sustainable and healthy food, making it available to a larger number of people;
- The development of Food Systems Living Labs will allow for the engagement of a wide range of stakeholders at a country-regional-local level to jointly tackle concrete, real-life (R&I) food system challenges, including unusual suspects and those who do not usually work together.

4.4.12. Other related Partnerships

Who are they? | This category groups all the EC's partnerships, currently existing or in the process to be created, of different typologies (co-funded, co-programmed, institutionalised, such as the Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking – ECB JU, PRIMA, EIT FOOD, etc.), related to FS. It includes also the Knowledge and Innovation Communities (KICs), and in particular the ones on food (EIT FOOD) and climate (EIT-Climate). To have an effective collaboration with them, FOODPathS will establish collaborations with the coordinators of the related partnerships, as entry/contact points for connecting with all the actors involved in them. In this target are included also the experts' groups providing resources to the partnerships, for instance, the [High-Level Experts Group](#) engaged by the EC in 2021 to assess the need for an International Platform for Food Systems Science to Policy Interfaces that is providing insights and indications relevant for the FOODPathS scope.

These actors should be closely involved in the communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities to guarantee the coherence of the ERA on FS, reducing gaps and fostering collaborations to increase the impact among all the

partnerships. Moreover, thanks to this, it would be possible to align and integrate all partnership activities towards the achievement of the EU strategic priorities (EU Green Deal, Farm to Fork Strategy, Biodiversity Strategy, FOOD2030, Fit For 55, etc.). They will be involved in a series of activities, from the definition of the SRIA to the support in the launch of the prototype.

Messages | The following messages should be transferred thanks to the activities of the CDE Plan:

- It is important to define common principles and objectives, to guarantee the coherence of the ERA on FS;
- Common activities are to be designed to improve the EU policy on FS and the alignment among the SRIAs;
- FOODPathS and other related partnerships can support and feed each other with their results;
- Establishing a discussion with Living Labs operating in the FS is considered a plus.

4.4.13. Coordinators of other funded projects

Who are they? | Another target audience is composed of coordinators of R&I grants operating in the FS at local, national, European, and international levels. Creating collaborations and joint activities with them will enable FOODPathS to integrate their results in its deliverables, map case studies, and define communication activities together to extend the project operation to secondary targets and/or to areas related to FS. For example, collaborations could be established with the networks of living labs and policy labs with whom the CLEVERFOOD project will operate; FOODPathS results could feed the GenB project campaigns on education in bioeconomy in children and parents, integrating elements on the sustainability of FS; the SRIA developed by the FoodSafety4EU project could improve the FOODPathS one and facilitate the engagement of the stakeholders belonging to its *Supporting Partners* network; etc.

In addition, collaboration activities will be established also with the clusters of Horizon2020 and HorizonEurope projects operating in the FS and created thanks to the EC's service of Horizon Results Booster.

Messages | The following messages should be transferred thanks to the activities of the CDE Plan:

- Collaborations are possible on a large number of activities and will provide mutual benefits;
- Working together will enable all of us to extend the audience and achieve a greater impact;
- FOODPathS looks for inputs and results (i.e. lessons learned, case studies, etc.) developed by other projects;
- Sharing the common reflection that individually we will not be able to tackle the huge societal challenges and reach SFS.

5. Dissemination and communication tools and activities

The achievement of the objectives of this plan will be ensured by the complementarity of its activities and thanks to the use of different tools and channels aimed to address identified stakeholders' needs and expectations. In this chapter, the tools used, and the activities implemented are presented in detail. Each of them will be designed in compliance with the HorizonEurope guidelines to acknowledge the funding received from the EU¹.

In the next paragraphs, each tool or activity is described, indicating the next steps, the FOODPathS partner responsible for the implementation and how the other ones will be involved in them. The tools and activities identified are the following:

- Brand Identity
- Website
- Database
- Press releases
- Social Networks
- Other (traditional) media outlets
- SFSN
- Podcasts
- Webinars
- Leaflets, brochures and factsheets
- Project presentations and articles
- Conferences and events
- Networking activities
- Other C&D activities

5.1. Brand Identity

Brand identity is based on the noticeable elements of a brand (for instance - trademark colour, logo, name, symbol). It allows the target audiences to identify the brand. Therefore, the logo is one of the key elements of the project's identity, whose main goal is to effectively represent the vision, mission, and core objectives of the FOODPathS project. Since the project adopts a co-creative and multi-stakeholder approach in all its activities, also the logo and its key element were developed by the whole consortium, in a process coordinated by EUFIC.

5.1.1. Logo

Before the kick-off of the project, EUFIC developed and shared a survey among the partners to gather their opinions on some elements that characterise the design of a logo (messages that it should deliver, preferred shape and colours, etc.)². Based on survey results, three options were developed and shared with partners during the Kick-off Meeting (KoM, June 2022), including the concept behind each logo and mock-ups showing how they appear on communication materials³. After an interactive process, which continued also after the KoM⁴, the following logo was selected:

Figure 2 – Image of the selected logo

The **chosen logo aims** to represent the following ideas (which are all aims of the project):

¹ Communicating about your EU-funded project, https://rea.ec.europa.eu/communicating-about-your-eu-funded-project_en

² The survey and the whole process is shortly presented in Annex II.

³ The document presented to and shared with partners during the kick-off meeting is available [here](#).

⁴ The whole process is described in Annex II.

- Developing partnerships for a better, more inclusive food system that involves and is fair to all actors, as well as being respectful for the planet and the environment;
- A pathway, a collaborative intelligence to establish innovative, effective, sustainable, safe and fair food systems;
- Bridging silos by mindful, co-creative and inclusive collaboration;
- Prepared for adversity and ensures sustainable food systems everywhere and in all circumstances;
- Sense of urgency: change is needed, and it's needed now.

Those **aims and values are represented in different ways** through a logo that aims to be modern and timeless, to ensure its longevity.

- The paper clip is the inspiration behind the chosen logo, it represents the idea of togetherness and the idea that change is possible if we work towards it together, in an inclusive way. It works to connect people and ideas, going from point A to point B, in a complex way. The curves indicate that the path ahead may be complex, but that it still finds connections and can change along the way;
- It connects the two words of the project name, representing the multitude of connections that are needed to achieve this better and sustainable future;
- The colour gradient indicates the transition needed in the food systems for a better future;
- The chosen colours and colour palette indicate a sense of urgency, willpower and determination but with optimism and positive thinking as well as energy and creativity.

5.1.2. Brand Manual

After the finalisation of the logo, EUFIC created a brand manual to guide partners and external users (i.e., web developers, the future Partnership consortium, etc.) in the correct use of the logo and its elements. The document is available to all partners on the internal project SharePoint platform ([here](#)), and it shows the different versions of the logo to be used, the specific font, colours and dimensions, as well as examples of logo applications on various materials.

5.2. Website

The website is the **entry point and the primary information source of the FOODPathS project**, informing about its scopes, activities, partners, news, events and results, and it will be connected to the project's channels and media (i.e. the SFSN and social media). **EUFIC will coordinate the website creation process, taking care of the WP leaders' needs and requirements** (i.e. the Hub of Living Labs, the interactive map of funders, etc.), **and be responsible for the technicalities**, including the selection of a supplier for the website technical development.

As a first step, EUFIC, after consulting WP8 core partners (ZonMw, INRAE, AU, IT, IFA, as well as FDE for his role in the Hub of LLs development), bought the domain <http://foodpaths.eu>⁵ and defined the first structure for the website, intending to collect quotations from potential suppliers. At the end of July 2022, after a selection process and meetings with some of the companies invited to send their best offers, EUFIC, after informing INRAE and IT, selected BoostU as a supplier for the FOODPathS website, which will be **launched in early autumn 2022**.

According to the contract, the website will be developed using WordPress as CMS (Content Management Systems), preferred to the customised ones because of its open-source nature. The **FOODPathS website will be hosted on the EUFIC servers, that are based in the EU**. According to the contract signed with BoostU, the website will be **maintained alive for 3 years after the end of the project** (till December 2028): during this period, the company will update the installed plug-ins, monitor the security and maintain the Secure Sockets Layer (SSL) certificate, thus allowing to users to browse the website without any issue.

Website content will be prepared with the contribution of all partners, meanwhile, EUFIC will be responsible for the last fine-tuning of the texts provided and for their uploading on the website.

Even if the design and framework of the website will be finalised after the publication of this document (and after a meeting with BoostU and two rounds of feedback), in the next sub-paragraphs the website structure is described, acknowledging that it could be slightly changed due to new ideas during the next stages of the website design.

⁵ The domain was already bought by EUFIC in June 2022. Moreover, also the domains sustainablefoodsystems.eu and Foodsystemspartnership.eu were bought, aiming at redirect users looking for these terms in the web and preventing that someone else could buy them with the scope to confuse people. At the same time, FOODPathS decided to buy also the foodpath.eu domain, to redirect users misspelling the project name, however this is already taken and not available.

5.2.1. Homepage

It represents the entry point of the website, containing simple and attractive messages for the identified target audiences to engage them in the project activities. Designed to guarantee users' accessibility and in line with the visibility standards, it will:

- connect the users to the other website resources, tools and sections;
- show in brief the latest news and next events;
- re-address the users to other project's channels (the SFSN and the twitter account);
- give the possibility to subscribe for receiving news and information on FOODPathS results and activities;
- show FOODPathS main contacts (coordinators, EUFIC team involved in dissemination and communication activities, FOODPathS generic email);
- re-address partners to the collaborative internal platform (SharePoint);
- inform the user about the cookies policy (giving it the possibility to choose the options in compliance with the current legislation) and know more about the policy privacy policy (prepared by AU);
- acknowledge the EC funding.

5.2.2. About

This section provides the main information on the project, showing⁶:

- fundamental information about FOODPathS (project overview, goals and approach);
- members of the consortium, with a logo and brief description of each partner (including their role in the project) and other information (i.e. partner website, staff involved in the project, contacts, etc.);

the FOODPathS Advisory board and its members, including each one's picture, the logo of the entity they represent and a short biography.

5.2.3. News and Events

In this section, all the news and upcoming events interesting for all the defined target audiences are shown in detail, including information on both the past and upcoming events. This page is connected to the preview available on the FOODPathS homepage.

5.2.4. Map of funders

This section will show an interactive map of the funders of the prototype for the future partnership. Users can navigate within the map, zooming and scrolling, and they can obtain more information about each funder by clicking on an icon: thanks to this, they can read the name of the entity (in English and its national language), entity category, website, contact information, etc. The map will be launched later and it will be constantly updated with the new funders supporting the partnership. The map will be accessible from the homepage, where it will be embedded.

5.2.5. Resources

This section will include all project results, documents, publications, and informative and awareness-raising materials produced by the project (articles, press releases, leaflets, etc). All the items collected in this section will be made searchable according to their nature (result, article, document, podcast, etc.) and/or targeted audience.

5.2.6. Branded network of universities and training programs

This page will provide information and visibility to the branded network of universities that will be created by FOODPathS and to the training opportunities offered by its members. Thanks to this section, specific target audiences will be informed and motivated in taking action in becoming the leaders of tomorrow's food systems

⁶ Personal information (i.e., short biography of AB members) will be communicated according to current legislation, other specific rules of the entities involved, and in line with the provisions of the FOODPathS Data Management Plan.

transition. This page will be launched at a later stage, when the network will be established (by November 2024 but probably before).

5.2.7. Knowledge Hub and Living Labs

This section of the website will contain an interactive visualization system that will provide an overview of all LLs spread all over Europe that are developing pilot actions and producing knowledge on the FS. The Knowledge Hub, one of the key results of FOODPathS (see §8.2.6), will reduce the current fragmentation on the FS-Labs, providing information about their work, tools and resources produced (documents, videos, etc.), website, contacts, etc. Users will have the possibility to search among them using keywords and filters. The Knowledge Hub will be defined more in detail during the next stages of the project, thanks to the direct involvement of stakeholders in its co-design. FDE will be responsible for the coordination of the design process, as well as for the selection of the supplier, and its launch is foreseen by 2024.

5.2.8. Other tools and elements of the website

The website will show the cookies preferences to the users making the first access, connect the users to the @SciFoodHealth twitter account (see §5.5), allow users to register to receive communication from the project (and enable the creation of the FOODPathS database, see §5.3), and any other widget or tools installed by website developers to address the identified scopes. Moreover, EUFIC will use an analytic tool to track the traffic on the website (in line with the GDPR prescriptions), to calculate the outreach.

5.3. Database

With the scope to spread the project's results and news, and actively engage relevant stakeholders in the FOODPathS activities, a database of contacts will be created. It will consist of:

- people autonomously registering on the website, mainly to receive information from the project about the next events and activities implemented;
- people participating in FOODPathS events that decide to receive also next information and communication on the project;
- contacts' details inserted by the partners (only strictly necessary personal information), about stakeholders met in other project's activities or of whom details (email and phone number) are publicly available: in this last case, they will be only individually contacted by partners responsible for a specific activity for which their involvement is relevant (i.e., invite as an expert in the mirror groups, meetings to explain the network of universities scopes, etc.). In any case, it is excluded that they will receive communications for whom they have not subscribed by themselves.

The database will be developed in **compliance with the GDPR and according to the provisions of the Data Management Plan** (DMP, to be developed by AU by November 2022), which will regulate also the partners' access to it.

5.4. Press Release

Press releases are being developed to raise awareness and inform the media about the project's main activities and results. Thanks to this tool, a larger number of stakeholders are expected to be reached. Press releases (at the national and European levels) can target both generic and specialized media, according to the main content of it. In any case, the press release targeting generic media and the large public will be developed avoiding scientific jargon; differently from the one targeting specialized media.

EUFIC is responsible for the development of the first draft in English of each press release, which is then shared with ZonMw and INRAE and other relevant partners (i.e., the WP responsible for the activities presented in the press release). When ready, the press release will be sent by EUFIC to journalists selected according to their relevance to the topic; moreover, the document will be shared with all partners on Sharepoint, inviting them to send it to their contacts through their press offices (also, in case, translating the press release in their language). Press releases will be made available and downloadable on the project website and promoted in the SFSN.

In June 2022, EUFIC and INRAE prepared the first press release to address the generic media about the launch of the FOODPathS project and to inform about the Kick-off Meeting.

5.5. Social networks

Social networks represent a way to communicate the project's activities and involve specific targets in FOODPathS activities. They will be used to inform stakeholders about project activities and results, to increase understanding of the complexity of Food Systems (FS) and the transition towards sustainable food systems, to stimulate systemic change with a common language, and to actively engage the identified target groups in the activities foreseen by the project, among others.

Having in mind these scopes, the project's target audiences and the messages to be conveyed, **partners have identified Twitter as the best social network to post regular messages** about the achievements and progress of the project, to engage stakeholders from selected target audiences in FOODPathS activities, increase the FS dialogues, promote project reports and events, etc.

However, considering the short lifetime of the project, the effort needed to create a good base of followers and the resources available, **project partners decided to not open a FOODPathS account, but to use the EUFIC's @SciFoodHealth one, counting >26.000 followers**. EUFIC will be responsible for the messages and posts, and it will then tag the partners, selecting the ones more relevant for each post. From their side, project partners guarantee strong support in retweeting and writing new posts inspired by the one published on the @SciFoodHealth account. However, **it is up to the partners to promote the project also through their social networks** (i.e. LinkedIn, Facebook, etc.), choosing the most appropriate one according to the message and the target to be reached. Also, in this case, **EUFIC will act as a frontrunner: it will prepare and publish posts on other social networks tagging the partners' accounts, that are asked to repost and give visibility to it. Moreover, EUFIC will prepare some guidelines for all partners on how to use properly LinkedIn to share content related to FOODPathS**. Finally, to effectively implement this process, EUFIC has collected all partners' social network accounts through a survey distributed before the kick-off meeting.

Benefitting from the already consolidated social media accounts from EUFIC and other partner organisations, **FOODPathS will promote** communication activities, such as podcasts and webinars, **and introduce the growing platform focused on SFS: the Sustainable Food System Network (SFSN, see §5.7)**. All social media posts will always include: a) the hashtag of the project (#FOODPathS) to facilitate the search for information on the project and see all the activities related to it; b) the project website), and c) the link to the SFSN platform inviting them to exchange their opinions and connect with other interested actors.

5.6. Other (traditional) media outlets

In addition to social media networks, for specific activities, FOODPathS will use traditional media outlets (e.g., newspapers, TV, radio, podcasts) to reach a wider audience and further promote the benefits that the future Partnership intends to have for society.

EUFIC will be in charge of identifying opportunities, tailoring the communication or dissemination activities (e.g., selecting which type of communication is best suited to the type of media outlet, the region and target group) and contacting, with the support of all partners, journalists and other communication experts working in relevant areas at a national and European level. Some examples include the release of an interview, distribution of informative materials, involving a FOODPathS partner as a guest during a TV show/podcast episode, etc.

5.7. Sustainable Food Systems Network (SFSN)

The [Sustainable Food Systems Network \(SFSN\)](#) is an online community dedicated to people interested in sharing knowledge, building new partnerships and collaborations, being informed on the latest news, and finding opportunities in the FS. **Launched in 2021 by the FIT4FOOD2030 project, managed and animated by EUFIC, the community counts >1.300 members** representing policy makers, entrepreneurs, researchers, NGO representatives, citizens, students, and others interested in being engaged in the FS. The discussion is organised on the FS at glance, as well as in thematic groups: currently one active on the microbiome, run by the cluster of projects "Microbiome4Life", and a second one expected to launch very soon on engaging citizens in the FS transformation (which will be run by CLEVERFOOD project). The platform has dedicated sections to:

- facilitate the exchange of knowledge about FS, called "Resources";
- promote events and invite other users to join them;
- opportunities for a wide range of collaborations (job offers, mentorship, internships, etc).

Each member of the community can publish posts (such as a social network), upload items in the Resources section, launch surveys, quizzes, polls, and promote opportunities, among others.

Figure 3 – Screenshot of the current main page of the SFSN

Given its characteristics, **the SFSN community serves as an ideal channel to connect and engage with specific stakeholders for the FOODPathS activities, and the wider community interested in the topic. FOODPathS partners are called to be as interactive as possible in the SFSN**, by posting on regular basis. The posts can include their personal views on topics related to Food systems, but also information about the project, its progression, publishing results, and news, promoting events and other communication campaigns, and launching consultations/polls, among others. When posting information about the project, partners will be asked to include the hashtag of the project in the post (#FOODPathS). The SFSN has the advantage of being able to be used as a repository, which is particularly useful for the exploitation of important outputs of the projects even after the project ends. As previously mentioned, the platform allows you to create events, which will be automatically sent to the whole community via email, allowing them to see and accept (or deny) the invitations to events and webinars in their calendars. This proactive feature allows us to keep the community updated without investing any additional effort or time.

In the case of FOODPathS, it is the perfect way to find and understand the interest of our target audiences and it is necessary to promote activities in the network that include them, such as workshops where everyone participates and feels part of the "change" and can give their opinion. The objective of having selected the SFSN as the main channel is to continue building a community that can provide direct feedback, can benefit and help to shape the Prototype taking into consideration the views of all the actors involved in its development and future functioning.

5.8. Podcasts

To ensure all communication formats are covered, audio content in the shape of podcasts will be created. Systemic change requires the actors involved to understand key concepts; therefore, the objective of the podcasts will be multi-fold: these will help consortium partners, funders, policymakers, researchers and interested citizens, etc. understand these key concepts, (e.g. system transformation, Responsible Research and Innovation - RRI, Science-Policy Interface – SPI, experiences from specific Living and Policy Labs, etc.) related to SFS transformation. Furthermore, they have the potential to reach a wider audience and share further in-depth insights into key concepts and speak a 'common language' that helps break silos.

A series of ten podcast episodes will be created and run over the second half of the FOODPathS project lifespan (starting from November 2023). The podcast format will consist of a dialogue or interviews carried out by a moderator and an invited expert. Each podcast will be conducted in English language (possible translations in national languages will be evaluated), and cover a wide range of topics related to FS, results, or key concepts. **The content of the podcasts will be developed by ZonMw** (representing the JPI HDHL) **while EUFIC supports and facilitates their development, promotion and dissemination**. Since their production is expected in a later stage, the practical implementation of podcasts will be defined in a later stage and described in detail during the second version of this document (expected for February 2024), taking into account the results achieved, the target needs and possible suggestions collected from the Advisory Board and the SCAR FS SWG.

5.9. Webinars

Audio-visual content, in the format of webinars, will be created to complement the audio content of the podcasts. The objective of these webinars, similar to the podcasts, is to ensure knowledge building, to increase understanding of key concepts related to RRI for SFS (e.g. system transformation, SPI, inspiring examples from the Living and Policy Labs, etc.) as well as to speak a 'common language' that helps break silos. They will also present examples of successful initiatives and cases to make the theory come alive and inspire audiences with personal and practical examples. In some cases, bad practices might be presented as this can serve as a learning point for future initiatives. To complete this task, a series of webinars with a Question&Answer format will be developed for all partner networks and future Partnership organisations with invited experts covering the wide range of disciplines related to SSFS. This series will be implemented starting from November 2023 until the end of the project, and possible collaborations with other webinar series developed by other partners (i.e., EFFoST) will be explored. **ZonMw** (representing the JPI HDHL) is **responsible for developing the content and webinar program, while EUFIC supports and facilitates their development, promotion and dissemination**. Since their production is expected in a later stage, the practical implementation of webinars will be defined in a later stage and described in detail during the second version of this document (expected for February 2024), taking into account the results achieved, the target needs, and possible suggestions collected from the Advisory Board and the SCAR FS SWG.

5.10. Leaflets, brochures, and factsheets

To give an overview of the FOODPathS main objectives and results, leaflets and factsheets will be produced at different stages of the project, according to the achievements reached. In particular, a first leaflet will be designed at the early stage, to explain the main project purposes and present the partners. Other ones will be produced according to the WP leaders' and WP Deputy leaders' requests and needs, mainly to engage specific and sectorial target audiences. In any case, INRAE and WP leaders will be responsible for the text draft definition, meanwhile, EUFIC will develop their graphic design.

To reduce the environmental impact, leaflets and factsheets will be available mainly in a digital version, meanwhile, they will be printed only when strictly needed.

5.11. Project presentations and articles

All FOODPathS partners are encouraged to present the project, their activities and results in seminars, public hearings, meetings, conferences and other relevant events, with the objectives to inform the target audiences and engage them, promote the project activities and their exploitation, contribute to the establishment of collaborations. Considering this, a standard presentation of the project will be prepared by INRAE and made available to all partners in FOODPathS SharePoint.

Considering the relevance of the topic addressed by FOODPathS, specific meetings will be organised with the SCAR FS SWG, JPI HDHL, JPI FACCE, and other relevant actors belonging to the FOODPathS target audiences (§4).

Moreover, articles for specialised magazines will be produced by partners, mainly to inform about and present the results of the project. A plan for publishing articles (containing suitable journals and reviews, a timeline developed according to when each WP will produce the results to be presented, the responsible partners for the article preparation, etc.) will be developed by EUFIC, ZonMw (representing JPI HDHL) and the WP leaders.

5.12. Conferences and events

During the entire project life, **partners will participate in events and conferences** with different aims according to the audience participating in them. A list of all relevant events, fairs and conferences will be drafted thanks to the collaboration of all FOODPathS partners by September 2022, thanks to a spreadsheet prepared by EUFIC and shared by IT in SharePoint ([here](#), with a dedicated page within the *Reporting Communication and Dissemination activities* spreadsheet).

This list will include both sectorial and large-scale events, such as:

- Sectorial events: International ISEKI-Food Conference, EFFoST International Conference, European Commission's R&I Days, European Green Week, European Week of Regions and Cities, ERIAFF Annual Conference, etc.
- Large-scale events: Maker Faire – European Edition, Researchers' night, Terra Madre – Salone del Gusto, etc.

5.13. Networking activities

The network is one of the main strengths of FOODPathS, as shown by Figure 1 in §4.3, that could be considered as a “**network of networks**”, completely in line with the mission to pave the way to the future EU partnership. In terms of dissemination, exploitation and communication activities, the **networks related to FOODPathS will be used as multipliers and as a megaphone to reach and engage the most appropriate stakeholders**. However, even if the network is large and covers many key players in the FS, **all the FOODPathS partners must commit to extending it, engaging new ones**: other networks, funded projects, associations, etc.

This activity is aimed to respond to the specific needs of each WP (i.e. stakeholders to be engaged in Mirror Groups, actors to be consulted for the SRIA, associations of rectors to be involved in the definition of the FOODPathS network of universities, etc.), as well as to define joint dissemination and communication activities (in particular to reach specific target audiences that are better addressed by other actors rather than FOODPathS, such as the citizens and consumers), or to increase the exploitation opportunities for the project’s outputs.

This joint effort on stakeholders’ engagement (in particular of networks under each target audience category) **will be coordinated by EUFIC together with the WP leaders and WP Deputy leaders** (mainly through regular meetings presented in §9.1), **but all partners have to be committed to this activity**. The networking will be then implemented through project presentations, participation in events and conferences, individual contacts made by partners, etc.

5.14. Other communication and dissemination materials

Other informative materials (e.g. cards to be promoted on social media, save the date posters, gadgets, roll-ups, etc.) will be realised to increase FOODPathS visibility, promote project results and engage target audiences. They will be developed on request and according to the needs of the WP leaders and WP Deputy leaders, thanks to a continuous and coordinated dialogue (see §9.1). Content will be provided by project partners and presented in an attractive graphic layout produced by EUFIC.

	Target audiences												
	Partners of [...] consortium	Network of FOODP athS partners	Policy Makers	Policy makers supp. org.	Actors of the FS	Educators	Research performers	CSOs and consumers org.	Citizens and consumers	Philanthropic org.	Financers	Other related partnerships	Coord. Of other funded projects
Brand Identity	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Website	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Database	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X
Press releases	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Social Networks	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Other (traditional) media outlets		X			X		X	X	X	X	X		X
SFSN	X	X		X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X
Podcasts		X			X	X		X	X	X			X
Webinars	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X		X
Leaflets, brochures and factsheets	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Project presentations and articles	X	X	X	X		X		X		X	X	X	X
Conferences and events	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Networking activities		X	X	X		X		X		X	X	X	X
Other C&D activities	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

Table 3 – Target audiences matched with the tools and activities presented

Legend

	Not addressed
X	Generically addressed
X	Primary target

6. Timeline

The following table presents the activities to be implemented until the launch of the Prototype (November 2024), when a more structured plan is needed. The table presents only the main activities to be implemented, meanwhile, the daily ones (posts on Twitter, promotional activities on the SFSN, etc.) are not considered, since they will take place all along the project lifetime, every week. This table will be updated every year.

Year - 2022						
Month	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication activities				Meetings	
June	FOODPathS Dissemination, Exploitations and Communication Plan (D8.1)	FOODPathS logo creation and selection	1st Press release creation and dissemination	Definition of the website requirements and selection of the website supplier		Kick-off Meeting and co-creation workshop for developing DEC activities together
July			FOODPathS brand manual and templates (.ppt, .doc, zoom background, etc.)	Website development	Website content preparation	
August		Preparation of a 2-page FOODPathS leaflet (1 standard section about the project + 1 adapted to the WPs' needs)				1st Internal Workshop (24.08.2022)
September	Defining a "save the date" template to promote FOODPathS events	Preparation of a 2-page FOODPathS leaflet (1 standard section about the project + 1 adapted to the WPs' needs)	Preparation of practical guidelines for partners (how to use the SFSN, how to report activities, etc.)			ExCom meeting - possible discussion on leaflets & other WP leaders' requirements
October	Adapting the SFSN to the FOODPathS needs		2nd press release to launch the SRIA	Website launch		Meeting with WP leaders and WP Deputy Leaders (T8.3)
November				Map of funders' development		

December			Factsheet to present the SRIA		Meeting with WP leaders and WP Deputy Leaders (T8.3)
Year - 2023					
Month	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication activities				Meetings
January				Map of funders' development	
February					Meeting with WP leaders and WP Deputy Leaders (T8.3)
March				Map of funders launch	
April			Factsheet to present the report of mapping results (D2.1)		Meeting with WP leaders and WP Deputy Leaders (T8.3)
May					Annual Meeting - 2nd Internal workshop
June					
July					Meeting with WP leaders and WP Deputy Leaders (T8.3)
August					
September					Meeting with WP leaders and WP Deputy Leaders (T8.3)
October					
November	Preparation of the FOODPathS Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan (D8.1) update		Design and implementation of FOODPathS podcasts	Design and implementation of FOODPathS webinars	Meeting with WP leaders and WP Deputy Leaders (T8.3)
December					
Year - 2024					
Month	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation activities				

January	Preparation of the FOODPathS Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan (D8.1) update					Meeting with WP leaders and WP Deputy Leaders (T8.3)
February	FOODPathS Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan (D8.1) update					
March			Design and implementation of FOODPathS podcasts	Design and implementation of FOODPathS webinars	Hub of Living Labs implementation and integration into the website	Meeting with WP leaders and WP Deputy Leaders (T8.3)
April						
May						Annual Meeting - 3rd Internal workshop
June						
July						Meeting with WP leaders and WP Deputy Leaders (T8.3)
August	Factsheet to promote the WP7 results (report on trade-offs and benefits - D7.1 and Toolkit for co-benefits and trade-offs with liaised actors - D7.2)	Design of a brand identity for the FOODPathS network of universities				Meeting with WP leaders and WP Deputy Leaders (T8.3)
September						
October						
November					4th Internal workshop - Planning the launch of the Prototype	

Table 4 - Timeline with activities to be implemented till the launch of the Prototype

7. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

A set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) were fixed to assess the implementation of the plan every 12 months. In addition to the evaluation, KPIs will enable partners to correct and re-address the strategy, considering also new emerging needs, external factors affecting the project and experience gained by the FOODPathS consortium in implementing foreseen activities. KPIs are built considering the ones contained in the Grant Agreement and new ones introduced in the first months of the project.

Tools, channel activities	Metrics method	Expected results
Website	Number of visits, content shared and appreciated (by the end of the project)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Visitors: at least 50.000 visitors Website contents (i.e., news, events, etc.) shared by external users on their SNs: at least 200 Appreciation of website contents (through like/dislike application): at least 200
Database	Number of registered people	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> At least 300 people registered to the FOODPathS database
Press releases	Number of journalists contacted and downloads	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of journalists contacted (direct email): >50 in total Downloads from the website: >50
Social Networks	Number of posts, Impressions, user acquisition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> At least 90 social media messages were posted on @SciFoodHealth with an average total reach of >70.000 impressions 10% user acquisition (for website) coming from social networks
Other media	Number of experts contacted	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> At least 30 journalists/communication experts contacted
SFSN	Number of posts and interactions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> At least 30 posts written by FOODPathS At least 1.000 interactions with the posts
Podcasts	Number of listeners (per episode) and platforms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of listeners: at least 100 Episodes are made available on at least 4 podcast platforms (i.e. Apple, Spotify, etc.)
Webinars	Numbers of views, per episode	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of live-watching people: 100 Number of watching afterward: 300
Leaflets	Number of leaflets and downloads	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> At least 5 digital information leaflets > 500 downloads in total
Project presentations and articles	Number of presentations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> At least 40 presentations of the projects made by partners
Conferences and events	Numbers of events, number of people reached	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> At least 2 events attended per partner People reached during the events: at least 1.000
Networking activities	Number of activities implemented and actors engaged	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> At least 50 networking activities (1:1 meetings, joint communication activities, etc.) At least 20 new stakeholders engaged

8. Exploitation

Dissemination and communication activities described so far are designed to increase the FOODPathS exploitation opportunities, thus realising the project expected outcomes and impacts. Therefore, it is essential to plan a strategy for the exploitation activity, which allows for realising the sustainability and the re-use of FOODPathS main results and achievement also after the end of the project and the European Commission funding. However, considering that this plan is delivered at the very beginning of the project (August 2022), when all results are far to be achieved, this chapter should be considered as a guide for future activities to be planned more in detail. Indeed, before the FOODPathS conclusion, partners must assess together the validity and relevance of the measures defined, as well as agree on eventual Intellectual Property Right issues to be treated with some exemption from the Consortium Agreement prescriptions. Indeed, **the plan will be updated in February 2024** and by the end of the project, **November 2025**, when **a final version of the exploitation strategy will be presented**.

Acknowledged this, the current exploitation plan is designed starting from the definition of the Key Exploitable Results (KERs, §8.1) that FOODPaths will produce, then a strategy is proposed, taking into account some criteria presented later on (§8.2).

8.1. Key Exploitable Results (KERs)

The first step is to identify among the various results that will be achieved by the project, the ones most promising in terms of exploitability, degree of innovation and impact. For this reason, a list of KERs was defined in collaboration with partners. As stated by the European Commission, a KER “[...] is an identified main interesting result, which has been selected and prioritized due to its high potential to be “exploited” – meaning to make use and derive benefits- downstream the value chain of a product, process or solution, or act as an important input to policy, further research or education”⁷.

As a general acknowledgment, it must be clarified that the list was created starting from an analysis of the deliverables, expected results activities that FOODPathS will generate from these resources, the KERs were extracted⁸, and the list could be revised in a later stage when results will be effectively achieved.

So far, the identified KERs are the following (in brackets are the deliverables from where they are extracted):

- Report of mapping results, (D2.1)
- Functioning FS approaches & observatory (D2.4)
- Innovative governance model, (D2.6)
- Manual of the prototype Partnership SSFS (from D2.7 and D2.8)
- Interactive map of funders (from WP3)
- Procedures for future funding activities and project support (from D3.2)
- Knowledge Hub and FS-Labs (from WP4)
- Network of universities and the charter for exemplary SFS universities (from WP5)
- RIPE concept (D6.2)
- Report on trade-offs and co-benefits (D7.1)
- Toolkit for co-benefits and trade-offs with liaised actors (D7.2)
- FOODPathS communication toolkit (from WP8 and M14)

Once more, we like to underline that the main aim of FOODPathS is to develop the Prototype Partnership SFS in such a way that the future Partnership Consortium can start right away their Program Activities; hence, all exploitable results will be considered from this perspective.

8.2. Exploitation Strategy

Each of the KERs identified before will be shortly analysed according to the following structure:

- **KER description** – an overview of the result, explaining what it consists of and when it is expected to be ready.

⁷ European IP Helpdesk- Horizon Europe Bulletin, No.4, 2021, p. 10 (<https://horizoneurope.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/01/Horizon-Europe-Helpdesk-Bulletin-2021.pdf>).

⁸ A KER could partially or wholly coincide with a project deliverable, however, this depends from the exploitability, degree of innovation and impact of each result considered.

- **Unique Selling Point** – what differentiates the result from the existing knowledge: this section highlights why an external stakeholder should be interested in benefits from the KER.
- **Target audiences** – identification of the targets (from §4) to whom the KER should be promoted and why they should find it relevant for them.
- **Exploitation strategy** – Actions to put in place to guarantee the exploitation and sustainability of the KER after the end of the project.

The first three points of the structure allow us to better assess the exploitability, grade of innovation and impact of each KER (three criteria that – as shown before – should be kept in mind to define a project result as a KER). Meanwhile, the last point aims to present the first ideas on how to exploit it. Indeed, at this stage, when the KERs are far from their implementation, the strategy consists in guidelines that could be followed in the future.

Finally, in addition to the exploitation activities identified in the following paragraphs, FOODPathS will benefit from the support provided by the EC on the exploitation activities thanks to the services and tools that it created for HorizonEurope-funded projects. In a later stage, and assessing case by case for each KER, the consortium could decide to request the Horizon Booster Service, to publish the results and knowledge produce on the *Horizon Results Platform* and its TV and apply for the future editions of the Horizon Impact Award.

8.2.1. Report of mapping results

KER Description | It consists of a public report presenting the results of the mapping activities conducted along several WPs of the project and on different topics. In particular, it includes the co-creation concepts (T2.1), the list of possible co-funders (T3.1), study cases collected (T4.1 and T7.1), the education programs (T5.1) and the first version of the SRIA (T6.1). **Expected by:** March 2023.

Unique Selling Point | It represents one of the key results of FOODPathS since it covers a large number of different topics. Indeed, it brings together and creates a picture of the current state of the art on the FS that, currently, is missing. This will support a series of stakeholders to have access to updated information all in a single place.

Target audiences | All the target audiences (except for the citizens and consumers) are interested partially or wholly in the results presented in this document.

Exploitation Strategy | During the project lifetime, it will be disseminated through conferences and individual meetings with stakeholders, to ease its uptake and reuse of the contents here contained. Some partners could start from some of its findings to participate in new funded projects to develop further some of them.

8.2.2. Functioning FS approaches & observatory

KER Description | This report contains the results of the consultation with MS, EC representatives, scientists, and stakeholders to define specific needs for harmonized monitoring of the European FS sustainability. Based on this, the document presents specific objectives and organisational structure for an FS Observatory. **Expected by:** November 2024.

Unique Selling Point | The document provides protocols for defining and monitoring FS from local to national to EU scales in a global context, as agreed with stakeholders during the project implementation.

Target audiences | Policy makers, policymakers supporting organisations, research performers: to set up the FS observatory and definition of the monitoring systems. Other related partnerships: to receive data and lessons learned to be reused in their partnerships.

Exploitation Strategy | Presentations and discussions with MS, SCAR WG FS, JRC, prototype co-funders, etc., aimed at the adoption and implementation of the proposed solutions.

8.2.3. Innovative governance model

KER Description | The document will contain a governance model proposal to be tested for one year by the prototype partnership elaborated by FOODPathS. It will be inspired by the results of the consultation activity done with stakeholders. **Expected by:** November 2024.

Unique Selling Point | It has the guidelines to make sure that the next partnership will effectively operate inclusively, in line with the stakeholder's expectations and needs. It represents one of the main results produced by the project, that will guarantee the long-term sustainability of the future partnership.

Target audiences | Policy makers and potential future partnership SFS consortium: they are interested in understanding how the partnership will work. All FS Actors, Philanthropic Organisations, Civil Society Organisations, other related partnerships, etc are involved: they can take inspiration from this document to improve the governance models of their partnerships.

Exploitation Strategy | The governance model will be shared and presented to the identified targets during dedicated meetings.

8.2.4. Manual of the prototype Partnership SSFS

KER Description | This document will contain the lessons learned and the main findings after one year of testing the prototype of the Partnership SSFS, as well as clear recommendations to be presented to the main target audiences. This will be arranged also in a summary version to ease the access and understanding of its content. **Expected by:** November 2025.

Unique Selling Point | The lessons learned, and the findings will be crucial for the long-term self-sustainability of the future partnership since they will enable potential future partnership SFS consortium to re-address its activities and way of operation.

Target audiences | Policy makers and potential future partnership SFS consortium: they will find guidelines to improve their future action in the partnership governance and implementation. Other related partnerships: they can take inspiration from these lessons learned to improve their activities.

Exploitation Strategy | The document will be disseminated through presentations to the selected targets, moreover, INRAE will prepare and present a summary with lessons learned to the EC and the SCAR FS SWG in a joint meeting by the end of the project. Moreover, FOODPathS partners will ensure that potential future partnership SFS consortium will uptake the document to improve the activities of the future partnership on SSFS.

8.2.5. Interactive map of potential funders

KER Description | To establish an engaged and open network of potential funders to join the future SFS PS, a mapping will be done as a first step (results feed into D.2.1). The potential funders will be displayed in an interactive geographical map, which will be publicly available on the website. Map expected to be launched in autumn 2022

Unique Selling Point | The interactive map will be the entry point to the setup of an aligned network of potential funders for the future PS. It will serve both as an overview for the funders and as info about the funders, and will thus be of great interest to the whole community involved in the development of the SFS Partnership. The aim and novelty is the envisioned great diversity of potential funders, stemming both from public and private domains as well as from national and regional levels, that can fund relevant sectors of food, agriculture, environment and health as well as science and education in general.

Target audiences | Policymakers, policymakers supporting organisations (mainly funding bodies), research managers, and applicants of the future SFS partnership funding.

Exploitation Strategy | The map of funders will be integrated into the FOODPathS website and will be updated along the runtime and beyond. It will be a valid source of information on and for potential funding partners for the future SFS PS.

8.2.6. Procedures for future funding activities and project support

KER Description | The document will contain guidelines and recommendations on transnational call procedures and funding strategies following a systems approach. In addition, a collection of valid supporting measures for future funded projects of the SFS PS will be established. **Expected by:** November 2024.

Unique Selling Point | Insights and knowledge from the various project partners and their networks will be valorized but also input and experiences gathered from the dialogue with potential funders in the funders forum events and possible surveys and consultations will be integrated. Thus, a real co-creation approach is envisioned which will also involve testing to clarify the practicability of the measures proposed. This should lead to less fragmentation and more aligned as well as innovative funding strategies, a systems approach for integrated

portfolio management and research programming (enabling more interdisciplinary and systemic research to be funded, as well as less business-as-usual research, more knowledge hubs, stakeholder engagement along the value chains, etc.).

Target audiences | Policy makers and funding bodies (public and private), European Commission, research performers, and applicants of the future SFS partnership funding.

Exploitation Strategy | Presentations and discussions with policymakers, funders and future beneficiaries, the European Commission, and other Partnerships

8.2.7. Knowledge Hub and FS-Labs

KER Description | A web platform, embedded in the FOODPathS website, that collects information about the Living Labs (LLs) in Europe working on the FS, the knowledge developed and the pilots run by them. Designed as an interactive tool and presented as a map, the platform will allow searching among its resources using keywords and filters, presenting the main results for each LL mapped. Moreover, the platform will present concrete cases (both successes and failures, informing about the main drivers that conducted to that results). **Expected by:** November 2024.

Unique Selling Point | LLs operating in the FS sector have created several outputs and results, however, they suffer a large fragmentation, and it is missing a map of the knowledge produced so far, as well as a tool providing an overview of who is working on what. These gaps will be filled by the Hub of LLs.

Target audiences | All: everyone interested in knowing more about the activities implemented by actors in the FS can have immediate and easy access to them thanks to this web and user-friendly web platform.

Exploitation Strategy | As a standard and basic rule, the platform will be available and accessible for 3 years after the end of the project, also thanks to the maintenance activities provided by the supplier selected for its development. However, it should be adopted by the future partnership, which will embed it in its website and take care of its updating. Moreover, FOODPathS partners could be interested in exploiting it individually (i.e. FDE, promoting it among its associated members).

8.2.8. Network of universities

KER Description | A brand to distinguish all the European universities developing or integrating curricula on SFS. Inspired by the model of other networks of universities (i.e. the Bioeconomy Network of Universities), this brand will guarantee the education of future experts and professionals implementing the transition toward sustainable FS. The brand will be created in line with the FOODPathS visual identity, to make clear that the project developed it. **Expected by:** November 2024.

Unique Selling Point | A label that can make universities more attractive for their potential students and that will train future researchers and professionals in line with the partnership needs and R&I identified priorities.

Target audiences | Educators: they are interested in improving their educational offer to students, as well as the visibility and reputation of their institutions. Citizens and consumers (in this case, the young people potentially interested in university courses on FS) look for high-quality educational opportunities, clearly recognisable in the sector. Actors of the FS: interested in attracting students who graduated from the universities of the network.

Exploitation Strategy | The brand will be promoted and kept alive after the end of the project by the members of the network, through a plan that will be co-designed in a later stage.

8.2.9. RIPE Concept

KER Description | It will serve to define integrated calls resulting in a portfolio of funded projects across the quadruple helix of Research, Innovation, science-Policy interfaces and Education (RIPE). To do this, the RIPE concept will be based on a model for complex FS capable of capturing insights obtained in diverse FS projects that are useful for R, I, P and E. **Expected by:** November 2024.

Unique Selling Point | Thanks to this, the future partnership will be informed with lessons learned for the modus operandi, governance model and funding strategies to monitor and analyse project outcomes that are relevant from a research, innovation, policy and education perspective

Target audiences | The target audiences are the potential future partnership SFS consortium, including the funding agencies. Secondly, target audiences will be the applicants of the future SFS partnership funding such as research performers, actors of the FS involved in innovation trajectories, policymakers (in interaction with scientists) and educators. All FS actors will be invited to share their thoughts and experiences to optimally synchronize R&I&P&E.

Exploitation Strategy | The exploitation strategy will be developed with partners in WP6 (starting point), WP3&7 (policymakers), WP5 (research and educators), and WP4 (innovation). It is too soon to define the first steps.

8.2.10. Report on trade-offs and co-benefits

KER Description | The document presents the best governance and implementation practices, in particular, the “SSFS deals” at the global, national and subnational levels, and the lessons learned from other best practices to be used as input for the Hub of FS LLs. **Expected by:** November 2023

Unique Selling Point | It shows best practices discussed with relevant player acting also at the global level.

Target audiences | Policy makers and potential future partnership SFS consortium: they can be interested in learning from other models implemented by others in different contexts.

Exploitation Strategy | Presentation in dedicated meetings and the mirror groups foreseen in the WP7.

8.2.11. Toolkit for co-benefits and trade-offs with liaised actors

KER Description | The document presents the results coming from the Mirror Groups and the mutual learning activities with other partnerships and global organisations. **Expected by:** November 2024.

Unique Selling Point | It is represented by the content of this document and, in particular, by the long-term vision and direction for a comprehensive and inclusive SSFS partnership; a toolkit for SSFS actions divided in and across local, national, EU-wide, and global scales; sustainability indicators for assessing the impact of this partnership (social, environmental, economic). Such content could be used by different actors.

Target audiences | Policy makers and other related Partnerships: they are interested in learning more from activities implemented by others.

Exploitation Strategy | Presentation in dedicated meetings in the frame of Partnerships and directly to policymakers in Brussels.

8.2.12. FOODPathS communication toolkit

KER Description | All the factsheets, press releases, infographics, articles, a toolkit for engaging stakeholders (M14), and any other communication and dissemination material produced to present the FOODPathS results to target audiences will be collected in a toolkit, stored, and made available online. **Expected by:** November 2025.

Unique Selling Point | The toolkit will provide easy and immediate access to the main results of the project, giving the possibility to all stakeholders to obtain a first overview of what was delivered by FOODPathS and guarantee access also after the end of the project.

Target audiences | All, since the materials in the toolkit can provide easy and immediate access to the project's results and activities.

Exploitation Strategy | The toolkit will be uploaded on the project website (kept alive till December 2028), in the SFSN, on the EUFIC website (in the webpage dedicated to FOODPathS), on the CORDIS FOODPathS webpage and on other EC services offered to Horizon Europe projects to promote their results. All partners will use all or some of the materials contained in the toolkit to present FOODPathS's main results in conferences and meetings after the end of the project.

9. Operational process for communication, dissemination, and exploitation

All FOODPathS partners will be actively involved in the implementation of the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities. EUFIC will organise 4 internal workshops to align the C&D&E strategy, (re) define KPIs and guide partners on how to execute all required tasks successfully. Establishing a clear basis from the start is key to creating a common language and understanding. The expected contributions from partners are the following:

- Implementing communication, dissemination and exploitation activities within the networks they manage or belong to, in their own countries and at the European level;
- Engaging stakeholders belonging to the identified target audiences in a meaningful and coordinated way (see below '9.1. Operational structure' regarding coordination of stakeholder engagement and related activities);
- Supplying events, news and updates for the web portal, as well as for other tools specifically identified
- Participating in a coordinated way at conferences, workshops, events, etc. to promote the project and its outcomes;
- Requesting support for communication and dissemination materials (flyers, save the date for events, factsheets, etc.) proactively and on time;
- Keeping track of all activities implemented, aimed to show the consortium outreach and address the expected outcomes and impacts planned.

To guarantee the involvement of all beneficiaries and their linked third parties, a management structure was created, as well as reporting procedures and tools, presented in this chapter.

9.1. Operational structure

EUFIC, WP8 leader, is responsible for the overall management and support of the activities defined under this plan, with the support of ZonMw as WP Deputy leader. The coordination of the contribution of all partners is mainly guaranteed through the direct involvement of the WP leaders and the WP Deputy leader. As agreed during the project kick-off, **a meeting will be organised with WP leaders** (or at least represented by the WP Deputy Leaders) **every 6 weeks approximately** (starting from September 2022) to align the implementation of the provision of this plan, the stakeholder engagement activities, the support requested to EUFIC in terms of materials needed and promotional campaigns of specific tasks, etc. When possible, the meetings will be merged with the ExCom ones (WP1), since the participants required on both occasions are the same.

EUFIC and ZonMw will be responsible for the organisation of the meeting (selecting a date and timeslot, sending the agenda and the link for connecting, taking notes, preparing minutes, etc.). WP leaders and/or WP Deputy leaders are asked to confirm their participation and invited to enrich the agenda by proposing points to be discussed. Moreover, they can invite other partners involved in their WP to participate in the meeting, if relevant to the agenda and if this can help to implement the activities more efficiently.

In addition to this and when relevant, EUFIC will contact directly all or some partners, according to the purpose, i.e., to update on outstanding results or activities, ask for support in the promotion of specific campaigns, request information needed for the implementation of the provisions contained in this plan, etc. To ease the process, EUFIC asked FOODPathS partners to provide the contacts of the people working in their press offices (available in SharePoint, on a dedicated page within the spreadsheet in the "[Contact List](#)" section), to be engaged only when necessary.

9.2. Reporting activities

All FOODPathS partners (including the third parties linked to the beneficiaries) are required to keep track of their communication, dissemination and exploitation activities, with a twofold aim:

- Monitor the activities implemented through the KPIs (and provide a timely assessment of the provisions contained in this plan)
- Tracking the outreach and assessing the achievement of the expected outcomes and impacts.

EUFIC, with the collaboration of IT, prepared a reporting scheme integrated into the FOODPathS SharePoint (*Reporting communication and dissemination activities*, integrated within the page "[Dissemination & Communication](#)"), allowing all partners to continuously report about the activities performed and the results reached. The structure and the instructions on how to use it were presented during the first WP8 internal workshop. The structure will be fully operational from September 2022 following the reporting information requested by the EC. EUFIC will

prepare and deliver a handbook (to be stored in SharePoint) to guide partners in the filling of the online reporting document.

In principle, FOODPathS beneficiaries and third parties should enter data in SharePoint as soon as they implement an activity. EUFIC will monitor the process and, in any case, it will contact all partners reminding them of their duties:

- Every 4 months, to have a general overview and up-to-date information ready for the ExCom meetings;
- Before every annual meeting, discuss possible fine-tuning of the strategy in a dedicated session;
- For the reporting period fixed by the EC, to update data to the preparation of the technical report;
- By February 2024 and November 2025, when an updated version of this plan and the final report on activities performed must be delivered.

9.3. Revision of the plan

According to the contract with the EC, **this document will be officially revised twice:**

- **By February 2024, when a toolkit for engaging stakeholders will be included** (according to Milestone 14), and the overall strategy will be reviewed in line with the results achieved and the comments collected from the EC reviewers, and being prepared to efficiently launch the prototype;
- **By November 2025, at the end of the project**, when the results of the communication and dissemination activities will be reported, and a final version of the exploitation strategy will be presented, identifying a detailed trajectory to achieve the expected outcomes and impacts.

EUFIC will assess the strategy every year, to be sure that issues and blockers for the achievement of the planned objectives and activities are spotted and managed properly in time. Indeed, as said in the previous paragraph, EUFIC will ask partners to ensure that they have updated the activities performed in the SharePoint, to present and discuss results achieved (as well as the lessons learned and the challenges met) during a dedicated co-creative session in the annual meeting, where possible actions to fine-tune the plan will be identified. Moreover, in the same context, EUFIC and ZonMw, with the contribution of all partners, will define the actions for the following year, updating the timeline contained in this plan (§6)⁹. In doing this, opinions and suggestions to improve the planned actions could be asked to the Advisory Board and the SCAR FS WG.

10. Conclusions and next steps

This document presents the dissemination, exploitation and communication strategy and activities designed by the FOODPathS project to reach project objectives having in mind the target audiences' needs and expectations. It includes the main tools and channels that have been identified to implement the planned actions, including the partners responsible for each of them. Finally, the plan defines a management structure to guarantee the efficient implementation, tracking and assessment of the activities.

The first three months of the FOODPathS project were mainly dedicated to co-create with partners this plan, discussing and clarifying key elements (targets, the messages to be conveyed to them, the identification of the KERs, etc.). To do this, a co-creative session was organised with all partners during the kick-off meeting, WP leaders and the WP Deputy leaders were consulted and asked to comment and integrate the first version of this plan between July and August 2022, and an internal workshop on the 24th of August 2022 (the first one the 4 planned) with all partners to agree and finalise this plan.

In the meantime, considering the urgency to start communicating and disseminating about the projects and their activities, partners – and in particular EUFIC, ZonMw, INRAE, IT, AU and EFFoST – started to implement some actions during these first three months (press release, brand identity, website content, first draft project flyers).

However, the next months will represent a relevant test for the content of this document: according to the results obtained from now to **May 2023, the strategy presented in this plan will be evaluated and fine-tuned during the next annual meeting, where a detailed plan for the second year of the project will be agreed upon.**

ANNEX I – Targets, needs, messages and future role

The following table shows what are the needs and messages for each target. Moreover, it highlights which will be the role they can play within the future partnership in the long term.

Target audiences	Target's needs (shortly reported)	Messages (shortly reported)	Potential future Partnership SFS Consortium	Potential Applicants of future Partnership Funding
Partners of the future Partnership SFS Consortium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facilitate synergies in ERA for SFS, R&I public and private funders to shape the FS ERA MS interested in the alignment of co-funded calls An SRIA integrating urban and regional FS strategies Need to support and liaise with ongoing initiatives to ensure holistic and inclusive approaches, avoiding ERA fragmentation and funding overlap Engagement of all FS actors including civil society, philanthropic organisations and consumers at large to reach sustainable FS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> FOODPathS project is paving the way for your future activities FOODPathS will work to facilitate the dialogue between the partners of the future Partnership SFS Consortium and all the other actors FOODPathS results will represent a resource for developing and improving the future partnership 	YES	NO
Network of FOODPathS partners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facilitate synergies in ERA for SFS, R&I public and private funders to shape the FS ERA MS interested in the alignment of co-funded calls An SRIA integrating urban and regional FS strategies Need to support and liaise with ongoing initiatives to ensure holistic and inclusive approaches, avoiding ERA fragmentation and funding overlap Engagement of all FS actors including civil society, philanthropic organisations and consumers at large to reach sustainable FS Education and training programs for the leaders of tomorrow's FS transition. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> FOODPathS is producing results that can feed and improve your activities; Convey the FOODPathS dissemination and activities within your network; Give contribution to the SRIA and other project activities; Support FOODPathS to engage stakeholders and motivate key actors in becoming co-funders Receive information and get involved in the co-creation of the future SFS partnership 	Partially YES	Partially YES

<p>Polymakers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facilitate synergies in ERA for SFS, R&I public and private funders to shape the FS ERA MS interested in the alignment of co-funded calls An SRIA integrating urban and regional FS strategies Need to support and liaise with ongoing initiatives to ensure holistic and inclusive approaches, avoiding ERA fragmentation and funding overlap Engagement of all FS actors including civil society, philanthropic organisations and consumers at large to reach sustainable FS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There is an urgency to act in implementing policies and strategies on FS and to critically review existing policies to stay within planetary boundaries We urgently need to build the governance foundations for effective FS management at the European level FOODPathS activities and the SFS partnership prototype will help policymakers to realize the sustainability targets and policies set at the National, European and International levels FOODPathS partners can provide actionable knowledge to improve policies at all levels A real commitment (policy development and resources) is needed to make the partnership work and implement the SRIA FOODPathS can contribute to guaranteeing the coherence of the ERA on FS and align the R&I actions and funds among different MS and governance levels while respecting different priorities Cities and regions can influence the FOODPathS SRIA FOODPathS will support more effective multi-level governance for food systems, including better coordination between European, national and sub-national actors (e.g. regions, cities) FOODPathS offers information on the future PS development and co-creation of important features, e.g. R&I procedures following a systems approach The development of FS LLs will allow for the engagement of a wide range of stakeholders at a country-regional-local level to jointly tackle concrete, real-life (R&I) food system challenges 	<p>Partially YES</p>	<p>NO</p>
<p>Polymakers supporting organisations</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facilitate synergies in ERA for SFS, R&I public and private funders to shape the FS ERA An SRIA integrating urban and regional FS strategies Need to support and liaise with ongoing initiatives to ensure holistic and inclusive approaches, avoiding ERA fragmentation and funding overlap 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Build a collaborative and structure to join forces toward sustainable FS R&I activities contained in the SRIA could address agencies' long-term objectives Working together, we can reach a stronger commitment from policymakers to taking the action in the future SFS Partnership The development of FS LLs will allow for the engagement of a wide range of stakeholders at a country-regional-local level to jointly tackle concrete, real-life (R&I) food system challenges Effective FS governance is key to building a more resilient European FS 	<p>Partially YES</p>	<p>NO</p>

<p>Actors of the FS</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An SRIA integrating urban and regional FS strategies • Engagement of all FS actors including civil society, philanthropic organisations and consumers at large to reach sustainable FS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engagement in the SRIA preparation and integration of the needs • The SRIA enables the uptake of innovations ensuring the transition toward sustainable FS • Existing barriers will be considered to reduce obstacles to the uptake of the R&I results • The Prototype sets the grounds for a platform where pre-competitive R&I actions are conducted, aiming for sustainable solutions for some of the current challenges. • The development of Food Systems Living Labs will allow structures at a country-regional level where thematic challenges could be tackled • Staying informed of FOODPathS initiatives has clear added value • The partnership will foster the collaboration of the actors of the FS with the public sector, as well as with other operators in the food value chain 	<p>Partially YES</p>	<p>YES</p>
<p>Educators</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An SRIA integrating urban and regional FS strategies • Education and training programs for the leaders of tomorrow's FS transition. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FOODPathS improves FS education by filling skills and knowledge gaps • The adherence to the FOODPathS European branded network increases the visibility of institutions and helps to attract more students • FOODPathS improves the quality and the content of courses • Curricula will be aligned with strategic R&I priorities in FS • Rectors and educators can be part of the participatory process to design training courses on sustainable FS • Educators' voices will be heard in the SRIA preparation • The development of FS LLs will allow for the engagement of a wide range of stakeholders at a country-regional-local level to jointly tackle concrete, real-life (R&I) food system challenges • Educators joining the FOODPathS network will have an opportunity to connect and exchange with pioneering universities across Europe, educators and universities' networks and to develop new collaborations 	<p>NO</p>	<p>YES</p>
<p>Research Performers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An SRIA integrating urban and regional FS strategies • Need to support and liaise with ongoing initiatives to ensure holistic and inclusive approaches, avoiding ERA fragmentation and funding overlap 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research centers' voices and points of view will be heard in the SRIA preparation • FOODPathS improves collaboration with policymakers to empower them with science-based information • The future partnership is a great opportunity to develop R&I activities in the FS 	<p>NO</p>	<p>YES</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Engagement of all FS actors including civil society, philanthropic organisations and consumers at large to reach sustainable FS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> FOODPathS can support the networking with other target audiences and increase the uptake of your research outputs The development of FS LLs will allow for the engagement of a wide range of stakeholders at a country-regional-local level to jointly tackle concrete, real-life (R&I) food system challenges 		
Civil society organisations and consumers organisations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facilitate synergies in ERA for SFS, R&I public and private funders to shape the FS ERA An SRIA integrating urban and regional FS strategies Need to support and liaise with ongoing initiatives to ensure holistic and inclusive approaches, avoiding ERA fragmentation and funding overlap Engagement of all FS actors including civil society, philanthropic organisations and consumers at large to reach sustainable FS Education and training programs for the leaders of tomorrow's FS transition. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> FOODPathS want to listen to the citizens' and consumers' perspectives and needs, including them in the SRIA and the prototype You will have their voice in the future partnership The development of FS LLs will allow for the engagement of a wide range of stakeholders at a country-regional-local level to jointly tackle concrete, real-life (R&I) food system challenges Give tangible examples of how they can participate and contribute Support FOODPathS in communicating correctly our activities and results 	Partially YES	YES
Citizens and consumers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> An SRIA integrating urban and regional FS strategies Engagement of all FS actors including civil society, philanthropic organisations and consumers at large to reach sustainable FS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Today FS are not sustainable: FOODPathS, funded by the EC, is preparing a joint action to change it; Benefits for the large public of having safe and sustainable consumption choices; FOODPathS will create an impact on your life The partnership will create new opportunities for finding safe and healthy food The development of FS LLs will allow for the engagement of a wide range of stakeholders at a country-regional-local level to jointly tackle concrete, real-life (R&I) food system challenges 	NO	NO
Philanthropic organisations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> An SRIA integrating urban and regional FS strategies Engagement of all FS actors including civil society, philanthropic organisations and consumers at large to reach sustainable FS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Learning from philanthropic organisations, (WP2, WP7, etc.) Philanthropic organisations welcomed the future partnership Increase awareness of the value of working on food actions to enable the transition toward a sustainable FS could be integrated into philanthropic organisations scopes The development of FS LLs will allow for the engagement of a wide range of stakeholders at a country-regional-local level to jointly tackle concrete, real-life (R&I) food system challenges 	YES	YES
Financers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> An SRIA integrating urban and regional FS strategies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> FOODPathS adds value to your investments thanks to R&I solutions easing the transition 	YES	NO

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need to support and liaise with ongoing initiatives to ensure holistic and inclusive approaches, avoiding ERA fragmentation and funding overlap • Engagement of all FS actors including civil society, philanthropic organisations and consumers at large to reach sustainable FS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • By becoming a partnership co-funder, you support the FS transition and create an impact on the society • Sustainable and healthy food price reduction thanks to investments in partnership-funded solutions • The development of FS LLs will allow for the engagement of a wide range of stakeholders at a country-regional-local level to jointly tackle concrete, real-life (R&I) food system challenges 		
Other related partnerships	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitate synergies in ERA for SFS, R&I public and private funders to shape the FS ERA • MS interested in the alignment of co-funded calls • An SRIA integrating urban and regional FS strategies • Need to support and liaise with ongoing initiatives to ensure holistic and inclusive approaches, avoiding ERA fragmentation and funding overlap • Engagement of all FS actors including civil society, philanthropic organisations and consumers at large to reach sustainable FS • Education and training programs for the leaders of tomorrow's FS transition. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Defining common principles and objectives to guarantee the coherence of the ERA on FS • Defining common activities to improve the EU policy on FS and the alignment among the SRIAs • Feeding each other activities with results achieved so far • Importance of establishing a discussion with LLs operating in the FS 	NO	NO
Coordinators of other funded projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An SRIA integrating urban and regional FS strategies • Need to support and liaise with ongoing initiatives to ensure holistic and inclusive approaches, avoiding ERA fragmentation and funding overlap • Engagement of all FS actors including civil society, philanthropic organisations and consumers at large to reach sustainable FS • Education and training programs for the leaders of tomorrow's FS transition. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaborations on a large number of activities and providing mutual benefits; • Extending the audience, achieving a greater impact; • FOODPathS looks for other funded projects' results • Sharing the common reflection that individually we will not be able to tackle the huge societal challenges and reach SFS 	NO	NO

Table 5 - FOODPathS targets matched with their main needs and messages to be conveyed to them. The last two columns highlight targets' future roles in the partnership

ANNEX II – Logo co-creation process

FOODPaths project is inspired by the principle of involving all actors in its activities, to deliver outputs that are the consequence of the integration of various expertise, knowledge and perspective of all partners. This principle inspired also the logo definition.

Before the kick-off of the project, EUFIC developed and shared a survey among the partners to gather their opinions on some elements that characterise the design of a logo. The survey had the following questions:

- Three adjectives to describe FoodPaths [open question]
- FoodPaths color is... [open question]
- FoodPaths shape is [options: soft/geometric]
- FoodPaths logo has [options: recognisable objectives/abstract icons]
- FoodPath message is [open question]
- Would you like to share other suggestions? [open question]

Replies collected were collected and used by the EUFIC graphic designer to create three logo proposals presented to partners during the Kick-off Meeting (29 June – 1 July 2022), asking them to vote for the preferred version:

Figure 5 – The three logo proposals prepared by EUFIC and presented during the kick-off meeting

With 71,4% of the votes (against 14,3% and 14,3%) the chosen option was the third one. However, before formalising the adoption of the logo, additional requests were formulated by partners to EUFIC. Considering this, EUFIC developed a new version of the logo, maintaining the style of the chosen one and applying other colours. Partners were asked to vote through an online poll between the two following options:

Figure 6 – Options prepared by EUFIC to address the partners' requests on the logo

At the end of this process, 11 partners out of 14 voted, with 57% choosing option 1, with the colours 'Cherry' and 'Honey'. As a result, the project has a logo and a brand identity that is the output of the whole consortium, rather than of one partner.

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